

CELLULAR IMMUNE RESPONSE AGAINST TICKS IN CATTLE VACCINATED WITH RECOMBINANT Bm95 ANTIGEN

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Abstract

The bovine ticks *Boophilus microplus* have been estimated to cause an annual weight loss of 0.7 kg/tick (Soulsby, 1982) and also spread serious haemoprotozoan diseases among cattle and buffaloes in India. Twelve healthy cross bred cattle of about 2 years age having no previous exposure to ticks were selected from Instructional Bovine Farm, RVC, Kanke, Ranchi (Jharkhand). Engorged adult *Boophilus microplus* female ticks were reared for hatching, larval emergence and tick challenge infestation. Bm95 recombinant tick antigen was obtained from Indian Immunological Ltd., Hyderabad. Experimental cattle were divided into two groups (A and C) of six animals in each. Group A was inoculated with 1 ml of Bm95 (200µg protein/ml) intramuscular on zero day and second dose in the same amount on 15th day after primary dose whereas group C kept as an unvaccinated control. All animals were challenged with 100 unfed larvae of *B. microplus* reared in laboratory on day 30, day 70 and 120 day post immunization (DPI). Cellular Mediated Immune Response (CMIR) parameters such as skin sensitivity test was highly positive on day 60 and 40 DPI in Bm95 groups whereas Lymphoproliferative response (LPR) was recorded positive only on day 50 and 70 DPV in Bm95 group vaccinated animals.

Key words: Bm95 recombinant antigen, *Boophilus microplus* antigen, Skin Sensitivity Test, Tick larval, Tick challenge and Cellular Mediated Immune Response.

Introduction

Ticks are the most common ectoparasites infesting cattle and other domestic ruminants throughout the world. The bovine tick *Boophilus annulatus* and *Boophilus microplus* have been estimated to cause an annual weight loss of 0.7 kg/tick (Soulsby, 1982) and also been found to spread serious protozoan diseases like Babesiosis, Anaplasmosis among cattle and buffaloes in India. In the early 1990s, tick vaccines were developed that induced immunological protection of vertebrate hosts against natural tick infestations. These vaccines contained the recombinant *B. microplus* Bm86 gut antigen. More recently, the recombinant Bm86 (translated sequence coded for a molecule of 650 amino acids, a predicted molecular weight of 71.7 kDa) has been expressed in *Escherichia coli*, *Aspergillus nidulans*, *A. niger* and *Pichia pastoris*. Of these expression systems, *P. pastoris* has been shown to be the more efficient for protein secretion. Furthermore, production of Bm86 in *P. pastoris* may increase the antigenicity and immunogenicity of the recombinant antigen. Keeping these in mind, the present investigation was planned to assess the Cell-Mediated Immune responses (CMI) in cattle inoculated with both the immunogens (Bm95 and BmWE_{Ag}) by measuring Skin Sensitivity Test (Intra-Dermal) and Lymphocyte Stimulation Test (LST) Immune response against *B. microplus* infestation in cattle.

Materials and Methods

Twelve healthy cross bred cattle of about 2 years age having no previous exposure to ticks were selected from Instructional Bovine Farm, RVC, Kanke, Ranchi (Jharkhand). Engorged adult female ticks (*Boophilus microplus*) were collected from naturally infested cattle herds in and around Ranchi. They were washed and placed in B.O.D. incubator at temperature 28 ± 1°C and relative humidity (R.H.) 85 ± 5 %. After oviposition, larval emergence were used for the preparation of antigens and challenged on experimental animals. Bm95 recombinant tick antigen was obtained from Indian Immunological Ltd., Hyderabad. As per the details provided by the

supplier, the source of the antigen was *B. microplus*. Briefly, Bm95 (*Boophilus microplus*), which is a concealed tick gut antigen was expressed in *Pichia pastoris* under the control of the Alcohol oxidase promoter (AOX1) by integrating the synthetic yeast codon optimized gene into the AOX locus. The identity of the protein was confirmed both by Western Blot and LC-MS (Liquid Chromatography - Mass Spectrometry). Final protein concentration in the formulated vaccine was 200µg/ml. Experimental cattle were divided into two groups (A and C) of six animals in each. Group A was inoculated with the first dose of 1 ml of Bm95 intramuscular on zero day and the second dose in the same amount of respective antigens on day 15 after primary immunization where as group C were kept as controls. For the assessment of Cellular Mediated Immune Response (CMIR), all animals were challenged with 100 unfed larvae of *B. microplus* reared in laboratory on day 30, day 70 and 120 DPI. These larvae were released on both the ears (50+50) of each cattle and ears were covered and tied with cloth ear bags (Fig. No-1). For detecting the degree and duration of CMIR parameters such as Skin Sensitivity Test was conducted on 0-day (before vaccination) after that 20 days interval up to two months then monthly interval up to four months where as Lymphocyte Stimulation Test (LST) was on 0-day (before vaccination) then monthly interval up to 6 months. The results of lymphoproliferative assay were expressed as Stimulation Index (SI) using the formula:

$$\text{S.I.} = \frac{\text{Mean OD of stimulated cell culture}}{\text{Mean OD of unstimulated cell culture}}$$

The criterion for positive lymphocyte proliferative response was set as 33% increase in S.I. of vaccinated cattle as compared to control cattle. Test of significance among the groups using two-way analysis ANOVA (Snedecor and Cochran) was done and by using Win STAT (2003) software system.

Fig. no. 1: Cross-bred cattle calves challenged with *B. microplus* larvae.

Results and Discussion

For knowing the status of CMIR, in the vaccinated group, there was evidence of redness and inflammatory swelling at the antigen inoculated sites up to 48 hours which reduced thereafter up to 72 hours. The values of the skin thickness (mm) after 48 hours of inoculation of respective immunogens was observed in Bm95

vaccinated group on day 60 (Fig. no.2) after that it was found to be significantly ($P < 0.01$) decreased on 180 DPI after third challenge (Riek, 1956; Wikel *et al*, 1978; Bechara and Szabo, 1984; Binta *et al*, 1985; Girardin and Brossard, 1985 and Das, 1988) as shown in Table no. 1.

Table no. 1: Status of skin sensitivity test in calves on different days before and after Immunization and challenge

Groups (No. of animals)		A (6)	C (6)
Nature of vaccine		Bm95	Unvaccinated
Before vaccination	0 DAY	2.38±0.05 ^a	2.37±0.05 ^a
Post vaccination	30 th day	^B 7.67±0.16 ^{bc}	^A 2.40±0.06 ^a
First challenge on 35th day	60 th day	^C 8.27±0.20 ^d	^A 2.35±0.08 ^a
Second challenge on 70th day	90 th day	^C 8.17±0.18 ^d	^A 2.28±0.09 ^a
Third challenge on 120th day	120 th day	^C 7.98±0.24 ^{cd}	^A 2.62±0.06 ^b
	150 th day	^C 8.00±0.17 ^{cd}	^A 2.65±0.06 ^b
	180 th day	^C 7.22±0.08 ^b	^A 2.38±0.06 ^a

Values having the same superscripts in column (small) and row (capital) did not differ significantly

In the present study, antigen-specific delayed type of hypersensitivity skin reactions was observed in animals immunized with Bm95 immunogens. Histopathological examination of the skin biopsies taken at the time of maximal reaction showed moderate accumulation of edematous fluid in the deeper dermal layers and excessive infiltration of mononuclear cells specially lymphocytes and macrophages in case of Bm95 vaccinated animals which might be due to multiplication of lymphocytes and release of macrophage

chemotactic factors by lymphokines. The vascular changes were probably mediated through the release of inflammatory mediators and lysosomal enzymes from macrophages (Roitt, 1988), leading to inflammation and swelling of skin at the injection site. This swelling became more indurated and indicated delayed cutaneous hypersensitivity reaction. This type of skin reaction was absent in non-sensitized control group of the animals.

Fig. no. 2: Showing typical delayed (48 hours) skin hypersensitivity reaction in calf immunized with Bm95 antigen.

The LST was conducted from the blood samples collected from all the groups of animals. The S.I. of Bm95 antigens stimulated cell were observed significantly ($P < 0.01$) higher Lymphoproliferative response (LPR) on 20 DPI, but a positive LPR (33% increase in S.I. of

immunized animals as compared to unvaccinated control animals) for Bm95 antigen stimulated cells was recorded on day 60, 90 and 120 DPI (Kumar *et al*, 2009) where as for Bm95 mitogen stimulated cells was on day 60 and 90 DPI as shown in Table no.2.

Table no. 2: Status of Lymphocyte antigen stimulation index in calves on different days before and after vaccination and challenge

Groups (No. of animals)		A (6)	C (6)
Nature of vaccine		Bm95	Unvaccinated
Before vaccination	0 DAY	0.654±0.007 ^a	0.656±0.016 ^a
Post vaccination	20 th day	^B 0.771±0.008 ^b	^A 0.657±0.013 ^a
First challenge on 35th day	40 th day	^B 0.917±0.008 ^c	^A 0.710±0.014 ^b
	60 th day	^C 1.150±0.014 ^f	^A 0.634±0.007 ^a
Second challenge on 70th day	90 th day	^C 1.222±0.035 ^g	^A 0.705±0.013 ^b
Third challenge on 120th day	120 th day	^C 1.124±0.019 ^{ef}	^A 0.719±0.020 ^b
	150 th day	^C 1.078±0.016 ^e	^A 0.734±0.027 ^b
	180 th day	^B 1.015±0.018 ^d	^A 0.747±0.017 ^b

Values having the same superscripts in column (small) and row (capital) did not differ significantly

Similar observations have been reported by many author who while studying the immune response in sheep (Rose *et al*, 1999) following vaccination with TickGard^{Plus} reported low S.I. in vaccinated sheep where as some are reported that immunization with *Hyalomma sp.*

tick antigens induces significant increase in cell-mediated immune response in rabbits (Manohar and Banerjee, 1992). However, the role of cell-mediated immunity against tick infestation is yet not clear.

Conclusion

Cell-Mediated Immune responses by measuring Skin Sensitivity Test (Intra-Dermal) was highly positive on day 60 in Bm95 groups of

animals, respectively whereas Lymphoproliferative response (LPR) was recorded positive on day 50 and 70 DPI in Bm95 group vaccinated animals as compared to unvaccinated control animals.

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